

Dosimetric Measurements Aboard the NASA WB-57 High Altitude Research Aircraft: Preliminary Results

Tristen Lee and Eric Benton¹

Atmospheric Ionizing Radiation Environment Institute
Oklahoma State University
21 February 2023

1. Introduction

Radiation exposure of aircrew and passengers at aviation altitudes is a topic of ongoing scientific investigation and public concern. Pilots and flight attendants are officially classified as “occupationally exposed” by the United States government. No occupation receives a higher annual radiation dose than aircrew, except for astronauts aboard the International Space Station. On average, a commercial airline passenger can expect to receive an annual radiation dose of about 3 millisieverts, which is roughly equivalent to the annual dose received from natural sources on the ground [Friedberg & Copeland, 2011]. However, frequent fliers, pilots, and flight attendants likely are exposed to higher levels of radiation and may be at increased risk for certain health problems.

Ionizing radiation at aviation altitudes primarily comes from galactic cosmic rays (GCRs) interacting with atmospheric nuclei and producing showers of secondary particles. Factors such as altitude, latitude, and solar activity affect the level of cosmic radiation exposure. On the ground, the atmosphere provides significant protection from GCR exposure. However, at aviation altitudes the atmospheric density is roughly half that of ground level and provides much less protection. The flux of air shower particles reaches a maximum at the Pfozter-Regener region between 60,000 and 70,000 feet. Relatively few empirical measurements of radiation exposure at aviation altitudes exist, especially measurements made in the Pfozter-Regener region. This is in part due to a lack of instruments available that can be operated aboard aircraft. Most radiation dosimetry instruments are developed for use in laboratory settings and require several auxiliary systems to function.

The Atmospheric Ionizing Radiation Environment (AIRE) Institute at OSU is developing the Atmospheric ionizing radiation Tissue Equivalent Dosimeter (AirTED) to address the need for instrumentation at aviation altitudes. AirTED is specifically designed to measure radiation exposure across a wide variety of aviation platforms. As part of the development and testing process, we have been fortunate to be able to fly AirTED on NASA’s WB-57 high altitude research aircraft. A unique benefit of testing AirTED on the WB-57 is that it is one of very few aircraft that regularly fly in the Pfozter-Regener region. The first prototype of AirTED was installed on a WB-57 in December 2021 and successfully completed seven high altitude flights where measurements of absorbed dose were performed.

The Earth is constantly bombarded by highly energetic charged particles originating from outside our solar system known as galactic cosmic rays (GCR). GCRs are composed of approximately 85% protons, 12% helium ions, 2% electrons and positrons, and 1% heavier ions. As GCRs enter the atmosphere they interact with nitrogen and oxygen nuclei to produce air “showers” of secondary particles. The showers can begin at altitudes as high as 100 kilometers and extend to

ground level. The cascade of secondary particles continues until the kinetic energy of the primary GCR is fully dissipated through electromagnetic and nuclear interactions. A single air shower can produce millions of secondary particles of different species and energies. Air showers produce a highly complex radiation environment, illustrated in Figure 1, consisting of multiple particle species that cover a wide range of energies.

Figure 1. Diagram illustrating the a hadronic, electromagnetic, and muonic components of an air shower.

2. The Ionizing Radiation Environment at Aviation Altitudes

At aviation altitudes, exposure to secondary neutrons produced in air showers are believed to be the dominant source of damage to biological tissue and play a significant role in potential damage to radiation sensitive electronics. However, neutrons make up only a small fraction of the total particle flux at these altitudes. In the interest of occupational safety, measuring the contributions of absorbed dose from neutrons is critical and requires the use of a radiation detector with increased sensitivity to neutrons. AirTED utilizes a detector that is particularly sensitive to neutrons called a Tissue Equivalent Proportional Counter (TEPC). The output of a TEPC takes the form of a lineal energy spectrum which is directly proportional to the linear energy transfer of the measured particles. Linear energy transfer (LET) is a variable that describes the amount of energy deposited

per unit length by a charged particle as it passes through a given material and is typically reported in units of keV/ μm . Neutrons tend to produce a high LET (>100 keV/ μm) signal in TEPCs, corresponding to a large amount of energy deposited over a relatively short period of time. Secondary particles at aviation altitudes relevant to radiation protection can have LET from 0.1 to 1000 keV/ μm .

Neutrons and other high LET particles make up only a small fraction of the total air shower secondary particle flux. The vast majority of the particle flux takes the form of particles that produce a low LET (<10 keV/ μm) signal including electrons/positrons, x-rays/ γ -rays, relativistic protons, and muons. Low LET particles deposit little energy within the detector, are difficult to fully resolve, and TEPCs tend to undermeasure their contribution to absorbed dose received. The TEPC used in AirTED is primarily sensitive to particles with LET ranging from 1 to 1000 keV/ μm . In future AirTED units we plan to include a second silicon-based detector that is sensitive to low LET radiation in the range of 0.1 to 10 keV/ μm . The combined measurements from detectors spanning the entire relevant LET spectrum will allow AirTED to accurately measure the absorbed dose from all relevant radiation present in the atmosphere.

3. AirTED Measurements Aboard the WB-57

On December 08, 2021, the WB-57 performed the first of seven flights with AirTED onboard. There are data from other flights yet to be analyzed due to a malfunction of AirTED's real-time clock. Timestamped altitude, latitude, and longitude data from the WB-57 were provided by the NASA WB-57 team and were used to produce the plot shown Figure 2. The flights varied in duration, flight path, and maximum altitude achieved. This was very useful in determining how AirTED performs in different conditions. AirTED's microcontroller records the output signals from the TEPC and stores a lineal energy spectrum every 120 seconds. The spectrum is then analyzed and dosimetric calculations yield the absorbed dose received during that time period (i.e., average dose rate). The absorbed dose rate measurements are correlated with geographic position and altitude. A single flight can produce hundreds of spectra, so a script written in Python3 was used to analyze data sets for each flight.

Figure 3 shows the cumulative probability distribution as a function LET (lineal energy spectrum) for combined AirTED measurements made across seven WB-57 flights. The measurements from the seven flights were combined due to the relatively low dose rate encountered in the atmosphere and the short duration of each flight. The probability distribution illustrates the likelihood of a given measurement having a certain LET value, revealing the contribution of particles with different LET to the overall absorbed dose. In this representation, it becomes evident that for any given particle measured by the TEPC, it is most likely to be low LET (<10 keV/ μm). Moreover, the probability of measuring a high LET (>10 keV/ μm) particle is over an order of magnitude lower than for low LET particles.

Measurements of absorbed dose rate and altitude for the WB-57 flight on January 20, 2022 are shown in Figure 4. The measurements show an increase in dose rate as a function of altitude with the highest dose rate occurring at approximately $\sim 60,000$ feet. The peaks in dose rate profile are indicative of individual air showers as they pass through the aircraft, showing that dose rate is not constant over time. This is expected due to the stochastic nature of air showers. If the sampling

rate of the measurements is decreased the dose rate would tend to an average value. Conversely, increasing the sample rate will highlight variation in the dose rates measured. Time resolution of dose rates is important to consider when comparing measurements to estimates calculated using models which typically give an average value of dose rate at a particular geographic position and altitude.

Figure 2. Flight profiles for seven flights with AirTED onboard the WB-57.

Table 1 displays the absorbed dose and dose rate values measured during seven high altitude flights as well as the corresponding estimates generated by the CARI-7A model [Copeland, 2017]. CARI-7A is a computer model developed by the FAA for estimating absorbed dose from radiation exposure during flight. CARI-7A computes the average absorbed dose rate based on the flight's latitude, longitude, and altitude. The WB-57 flight path data were used to reconstruct each WB-57 flight path in CARI-7A and calculate estimates of absorbed dose rate. AirTED is equipped with a real-time clock, allowing for a direct comparison of measurements with model estimates using the WB-57 flight path information provided.

On average, AirTED measurements of absorbed dose and dose rate were 34% lower than the corresponding model estimates across all seven flights. Flights with shorter durations (12/8/21 and 1/13/22) showed a higher percent difference than longer flights. The difference between the measurements and model estimates is not unexpected, as TEPCs are relatively insensitive to low LET radiation which makes up the majority of the secondary particle flux at aviation altitudes (Figure 3). Future AirTED designs will include a silicon-based detector to improve low LET

measurements below 10 keV/μm. Increasing the sensitivity of AirTED to low LET radiation should bring better agreement between measurements and model estimates.

Figure 3. The cumulative probability distribution for AirTED measurements across all seven flights.

4. Conclusions

AirTED is a radiation dosimeter in development by the AIRE Institute designed to measure absorbed dose at aviation altitudes aboard a variety of aviation platforms. As part of the testing process, AirTED was installed on NASA's WB-57 high altitude research aircraft and recorded over 23 hours of dosimetric measurements across seven flights. AirTED's measurements of absorbed dose and dose rate were lower than model estimates provided by CARI-7A. The disagreement between AirTED measurements and model estimates is not surprising due to the majority of the particle flux at aviation altitudes being low LET (<10 keV/μm), and the relative insensitivity of TEPCs to low LET particles. To address this, future AirTED designs will include a second detector based on a silicon diode that is more sensitive to low LET radiation. The combination of TEPC and silicon-based detectors will enhance AirTED's ability to measure the absorbed dose delivered by particles over the entire relevant LET spectrum and give presumably better agreement with model estimates.

Overall, the data obtained from the WB-57 flights has been invaluable to the ongoing development of AirTED. Flying AirTED on the WB-57 has allowed us to validate many of our design assumptions in real-world settings across a variety of operating conditions. Technical difficulties were anticipated, and we are grateful that the WB-57 team effectively communicated these issues

to us when they arose. This allowed us to gain valuable insights to the instrument’s shortcomings and will ensure that future versions of AirTED exceed the operational capabilities of the prototype.

Figure 4. Absorbed dose rate measurements for a single WB-57 light occurring on 01/20/22.

Table 1. Absorbed dose and dose rate measurements and model estimates calculated using CARI-7A for NASA WB-57 flights in 2021/22 [Copeland, 2017].

Flight Date	12/8	12/20	1/13	1/14	1/20	2/11	2/15
Flight Duration (hrs)	1.36	3.76	1.96	3.33	4.30	3.43	4.89
Measured Absorbed Dose (mGy)	2.1	10.8	3.4	8.4	9.7	7.1	12.8
Average Measured Absorbed Dose Rate (mGy/hr)	1.5	2.9	1.7	2.5	2.3	2.1	2.6
Modeled Absorbed Dose (mGy)	3.8	14.1	5.9	12.1	14.3	11.7	18.2
Average Modeled Absorbed Dose Rate (mGy/hr)	2.8	3.7	3.0	3.7	3.3	3.4	3.7
Percent Difference	46	23	43	30	30	40	30

Acknowledgements

The Atmospheric Ionizing Radiation Environment Institute at OSU thanks the WB-57 team at the NASA Johnson Space Center including Peter Layshock, Mallory Yates and especially Brad Laborde for their help and allowing us to carryout these measurements.

References

[Friedberg & Copeland, 2011] W. Friedberg and K. Copeland, *Ionizing Radiation in Earth's Atmosphere and in Space Near Earth*, Federal Aviation Administration, 2011.

[Copeland, 2017] Copeland, K., (2017) "CARI-7A: Development and Validation," *Rad. Prot. Dos.* **175** (4) pp. 419-431.

¹ eric.benton@okstate.edu